

Foreign Language Anxiety in French and Italian Online Learning

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Abstract

This study builds upon the research carried out during emergency remote teaching (ERT) at Croatian universities, implemented in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Participants were students of philological and non-philological study programs who were learning French and Italian. The purpose of the present study has been to measure foreign language anxiety in French and Italian online learning. For that purpose, we developed and validated the Foreign Language Online Learning Anxiety Scale (FLOLAS). This study compared the anxiety levels of the group learning French and the group learning Italian. Results revealed no statistically significant difference between the two groups, with both groups showing average anxiety levels below the theoretical midpoint of the scale. The correlation between four variables was examined (the duration of foreign language learning of the respondents, their language proficiency level, their online learning experience, and features specific to online learning). This was done by using the FLOLAS on the total sample and the two sub-samples included in this study. Students showing higher anxiety levels on the FLOLAS have a more negative experience with online learning. Anxiety was not correlated with their language proficiency, but it was correlated with the duration of their learning of French or Italian. The insights gained from this study can be used to develop strategies to mitigate the impact of foreign language anxiety in online learning environments.

Keywords: *foreign language anxiety, foreign language anxiety scale, online learning, French, Italian.*

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Introduction

Foreign language anxiety (FLA) significantly affects language learners' performance and overall learning experience. Horwitz et al. (1986: 128) defined foreign language anxiety as “a distinct complex of self-perceptions, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors related to classroom language learning arising from the uniqueness of the language learning process”. The topic of foreign language classroom anxiety has been researched since the 1980s (Russel, 2020). In the context of learning a foreign language

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through online environments such as e-learning platforms and distance learning, in regular online learning settings, or in emergency remote teaching (ERT) which took place during the COVID-19 global pandemic, language anxiety can play an important role in shaping learners' outcomes. Recently, numerous authors have been researching how foreign language anxiety in online environments affects the process of learning a foreign language (e.g. Hurd 2007, 2008, 2010; Pichette, 2009; Donahoe, 2010; Dixson, 2015; Martin & Alvarez, 2017; Selami, 2018; Chametzky, 2019; Russell, 2020; Kaisar & Chowdury, 2020; Seidikenova et al. 2020; Resnik & Dewaele, 2021; Novak Lađarević, 2021; Behforouz et al. 2022; Najeh Bel'Kiry, 2022; Véliz-Campos et al. 2023; Li & Du, 2023). This is due to an ever-increasing shift toward online learning in education after the spring of 2020, when the response to the pandemic was to move teaching to online platforms on a global scale for the first time. The increasing online teaching calls for research into numerous effects that FLA can have in an online learning environment and the ways how to mitigate anxiety and create a positive and stimulating learning environment.

Purpose of the study

In the spring of 2021, we conducted online research at four Croatian universities among students from philological and non-philological study programs who were learning French and Italian as a foreign language. Due to the Coronavirus pandemic, the teaching was done online. This research resulted in the publication of the paper *Emergency Remote Learning of French and Italian as a Foreign Language* (Režić Tolj & Viočić-Koprivec, 2022). The questionnaire designed by the authors, which was used in that research, contained several questions relating to FLA in French and Italian online learning. Responses to these questions have not been studied so far and they are the subject matter of this paper. The purpose was to research foreign language anxiety in learners' online learning experience. Based on the processing of the data from the mentioned questionnaire, a scale for the measuring of FLA in an online environment was created. The correlation of foreign language anxiety in online learning with the following research variables was examined: the respondents' duration of foreign language learning, their experience with online learning, their language proficiency level, and features specific to online learning.

Materials and Methods

Participants of this study were 206 students from philological and non-philological study programs of the University of Dubrovnik, University of Split, University of Zadar, and University of Zagreb who were learning French (N = 106; 51.5%), and Italian (N = 100; 48.5%) as a foreign language. Most of the students who participated in this research were students of humanities (53.4% vs. 46.6% students of various social and artistic study programs), 84% were undergraduate students and 16% were graduate students. The research was conducted online.

For this study, 9 items from the questionnaire created by the authors were extracted, all of them relating to FLA, which were not examined in the previous paper. On a Likert scale from 1-5, students had to evaluate how much a certain item relates to them by choosing their response according to the following legend: 1–It does not relate to me at all; 2–It mostly does not relate to me; 3–I cannot state that it either relates or does not relate to me; 4–It mostly relates to me; 5–It fully relates to me. The Foreign Language Online Learning Anxiety Scale (FLOLAS) was created based on their responses.

In the questionnaire, along with general data, students stated precise information about the duration of their learning of the French/Italian language. They assessed their language proficiency level according to the language proficiency levels referred to in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (A1–Elementary user; A2–Pre-intermediate user; B1–Intermediate user; B2–Upper-intermediate user; C1–Advanced user; C2–Proficient user). The students evaluated their online learning experience by using the usual grading scale from 1–Fully negative experience, to 5–Fully positive experience. On a Likert scale from 1–It does not relate to me at all, to 5–It fully relates to me, they expressed their level of agreement with 18 items designed for the previous study which examined students’ perceptions about the features specific to online learning of the French and Italian language in the ERT context. These results were presented in the paper *Emergency Remote Learning of French and Italian as a Foreign Language* (Režić Tolj & Violić-Koprivec, 2022), and they have been used in this study as variables to research the correlation of FLA in French and Italian online learning with the duration of foreign language learning, online learning experience, language proficiency level and features specific to online learning.

Results

Checking the Metric Features of the Foreign Language Online Learning Anxiety Scale (FLOLAS)

From the questionnaire created by the authors, 9 items were extracted that relate to FLA in the French and Italian foreign language online learning. All items were rated by the respondents on a five-grade scale (1–It does not relate to me at all, 5–It fully relates to me). Most of the items were formulated so that a higher score indicates greater anxiety in foreign language learning, while three items (1, 3, 7) were formulated oppositely, i.e. less agreement with the item shows greater anxiety. The initial Online Foreign Language Learning Anxiety Scale consisted of the following 9 items.

1. I feel relaxed.
2. I'm afraid when I need to actively participate.
3. I don't worry if I make mistakes.
4. I feel uncomfortable answering the teacher's questions.
5. I am afraid that I won't understand the content.
6. I feel nervous during classes.
7. I feel relaxed when giving an oral presentation in French/Italian.
8. I feel anxious during classes.
9. During exams, my heart pounds strongly, and my palms sweat.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test was conducted as a measure of sample adequacy (.90), along with Bartlett's test of sphericity ($\chi^2 = 543.06$, $df = 36$, $p = .000$), both of which indicated that the matrix was suitable for factor analysis. The statistical significance of Bartlett's test suggests that the data matrix differs from the identity matrix, where the correlations between variables would be zero. The KMO value is above .60, which, according to Tabachnick and Fidell (2013), is a desirable condition for performing factor analysis.

An initial exploratory factor analysis using the principal axis method and scree plot analysis revealed the presence of one factor with an eigenvalue greater than 1, specifically with a value of 4.91, explaining 54.58% of the variance. Based on the factor loadings and the reliability analysis of the scale (Cronbach's alpha), as well as the corrected item-total correlation, it was decided to retain only items with high factor loadings, i.e. those that have a strong correlation with the total score and whose exclusion would increase the reliability of the scale. According to these criteria, items 3 („I don't worry if I make mistakes“) and 9 („During exams, my heart pounds strongly, and my palms sweat“) were excluded, as their factor loadings were -.55 and .59, respectively, and their item-total correlations were .53 and .56, respectively. After that, another exploratory factor analysis using the principal axis method was conducted. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test, as a measure of sample adequacy, was .89, and Bartlett's test of sphericity was $\chi^2 = 460.65$, $df = 21$, $p = .000$, both indicating the adequacy of the matrix for factor analysis. A one-factor structure was obtained, with an eigenvalue of 4.23, explaining 61.07% of the variance. The analysis of factor loadings showed that all items had excellent loadings, which were -.72, .89, .77, .75, .84, -.74, and .74, respectively. According to Comrey and Lee (1992), factor loadings greater than .71 are considered excellent, loadings of .63 are very good, loadings of .55 are good, loadings of .45 are acceptable, and loadings below .32 are weak and should not be interpreted (Comrey & Lee, 1992).

After that, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted with the items numbered 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 on a sample of 103 respondents. A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was also conducted on the second sample ($N = 103$) using the AMOS program. Several fit indices were used, including the chi-square index (χ^2), the chi-square/degrees of freedom ratio (χ^2/df), the comparative fit index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), and the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA). The recommended values for acceptable model fit (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson 2010; Schumacker & Lomax, 2010) are: for χ^2/df , a value below 3.0 is considered acceptable; CFI and TLI values should be greater than or equal to .90; the RMSEA value should be less than or equal to .08. First, an analysis of the assessment of multivariate normality was conducted, and the overall kurtosis index was determined. Byrne (2010) suggests that multivariate kurtosis values greater than 5 indicate a deviation from multivariate normality. The obtained value of multivariate kurtosis was 27.56, so a bootstrapping procedure using 200 samples was employed. The obtained χ^2 value was 51.76, $\chi^2/df = 3.70$, $p = .000$, which indicated a poor fit between the data and the theoretical model. An analysis of the modification indices revealed a high modification index for error covariances between item 6 and item 8 ($MI = 20.30$) and between error covariances for item 1 and item 8 ($MI = 10.00$). Since items 6 („I feel nervous during classes.“) and 8 („I feel anxious during classes.“) were highly content-congruent, we decided to delete item 6 from the scale instead of adding additional correlations to the model. A new CFA without item 6 yielded a χ^2 value of 23.38, $\chi^2/df = 9$, $p = .0054$, which also indicated a poor fit between the data and the theoretical model. The analysis of the modification indices showed a high covariance ($MI = 13.23$) between item 1 („I feel relaxed.“) and item 8 („I feel anxious during classes.“), and one solution was to introduce a constraint correlation between the errors of these two items, while another possible solution was to delete item 1. The CFA conducted with one constraint correlation between items 1 and 8 yielded a good model fit with a χ^2 value of 9.35, $\chi^2/df = 1.17$, $p = .31$, $TLI = .992$, $CFI = .996$, $RMSEA = .04$. However, we opted for a simpler model without the need to introduce additional correlations, and we conducted a new analysis without item 1, which resulted in a good fit between the data

and the theoretical model. The obtained χ^2 value was 6.32, $\chi^2/df = 1.26$, $p = .27$, TLI = .99, CFI = .99, RMSEA = .05. However, it should be noted that the CFA used in this way was used as an exploratory, rather than a confirmatory analysis. Therefore, with the final version of the scale, which includes items 2, 4, 5, 7, and 8, we conducted another CFA on sample 1 used for the EFA. The data also showed a good fit with the model, with a χ^2 value of 5.98, $\chi^2/df = 1.20$, $p = .31$, TLI = .99, CFI = .99, RMSEA = .04. Using the principal axis method, one factor was obtained, explaining 61.63% of the variance. It is recommended to verify the factor structure of the scale on a new sample.

Table 1. Foreign Language Online Learning Anxiety Scale (FLOLAS)

Item	Factor loading
I'm afraid when I need to actively participate.	.93
I feel uncomfortable answering the teacher's questions.	.76
I am afraid that I won't understand the content.	.78
I feel relaxed when giving an oral presentation in French/ Italian	-.77
I feel anxious during classes.	.67

Legend: Factor analysis using the principal axis method, N = 103

Table 1 shows the items of the final scale and their factor loadings. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to check reliability. The obtained reliability index for the final scale of five items on the first subsample was .89, indicating a good internal consistency reliability. Reliability was also tested on the second subsample, where it was .87, also indicating good reliability.

FLA in French and Italian Online Learning

The results of this study showed that language anxiety is present among online language learners. In a study conducted by Wang (2023), it was found that FLA is present in online learning of French as a foreign language, with approximately half of the respondents learning French experiencing moderate or even high levels of anxiety. In this study, comparing the level of anxiety between the group learning French and the group learning Italian, no statistically significant difference was found ($t = 0.46$, $p > .05$), and in both groups, the average anxiety was below the theoretical midpoint of the scale (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison of FLA in French and Italian Online Learning

Variable	Subsample for French (N = 106)		Subsample for Italian (N = 100)		t
	M+ / SD	Actual range	M+ / SD	Actual range	
FLA in online learning	2.66 +/- 1.03	1.00 – 5.00	1.00 +/- 4.80	1.00 – 5.00	0.46

The Correlation between Anxiety in French and Italian Online Learning and the Study Variables

The created scale of anxiety in French and Italian online learning was further tested for correlation with the following variables: the respondents' duration of foreign language learning, their experience with online learning, their language proficiency level, and features specific to online learning (Tables 3 and 4).

Table 3. Correlation between the Results on the FLOLAS and Duration of the French and Italian Language Learning, Respondents' Experience with Online Learning, and Their Language Proficiency Level, for the Total Sample and the Subsamples for French and Italian

Variable	Subsample for French (N = 106)	Subsample for Italian (N = 100)	Total sample (N = 206)
	Correlation coefficient r	Correlation coefficient r	Correlation coefficient r
Duration of foreign language learning	-.20*	-.24*	-.22*
Experience with online learning	-.20*	-.33**	-.23**
Language proficiency level	-.13	-.10	-.12

Note: **p < .01, *p < .05

According to the results from the previous study (Režić Tolj & Violić-Koprivec, 2022), a statistically significant difference was found in the duration of learning of these two foreign languages ($t = -5.45, p < .001$). Italian is learned significantly longer than French ($M = 5.98, SD \pm 3.91$), i.e. five years on average, while French is learned for an average of three years ($M = 3.34, SD \pm 2.93$) (Režić Tolj & Violić-Koprivec, 2022: 44). Table 3 shows that foreign language anxiety is negatively correlated with the duration of foreign language learning, meaning that those who had been learning French and Italian longer experienced less anxiety in online learning (French subsample $r = -.20, p < .05$; Italian subsample $r = -.24, p < .05$).

The previous study established that students who were learning Italian evaluated their online learning experience more positively than the students who were learning French, and this was statistically significant (Režić Tolj & Violić-Koprivec, 2022: 47). By correlating the results on the Foreign Language Online Learning Anxiety Scale with this data, it was found that anxiety in French and Italian online learning is negatively correlated with respondents' experience with online learning. In other words, those who had higher levels of anxiety had a more negative experience with online teaching (French subsample $r = -.20, p < .05$; Italian subsample $r = -.33, p < .01$).

The participants self-assessed their language proficiency level in French, i.e., Italian language according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2). In the French language subsample, 36.8% of the participants were at level A1, 28.3% at level A2, 17.9% at level B1, 16% at level B2, 0.9% at level C1 and 0% at level C2. In the Italian language subsample, 31.1% of the participants were at level A1, 23.8% at level A2, 23.8% at level B1, 18.9% at level B2, 1.9% at level C1 and 0.5% at level C2 (Režić Tolj & Violić-Koprivec, 2022: 43). Foreign language anxiety in online learning was not found to be correlated with language proficiency level (French subsample $r = -.13, p > .05$; Italian subsample $r = -.10, p > .01$).

Table 4. Correlation between the Results on the FLOLAS and Features Specific to Online Learning, for the Total Sample and the Subsamples for French and Italian

Features specific to online learning	Subsample for French (N=106)	Subsample for Italian (N=100)	Total sample (N=206)
	Correlation coefficient r	Correlation coefficient r	Correlation coefficient r
1. I find online learning of French/Italian interesting.	-.30**	-.35**	-.32**
2. Technical difficulties (e.g., poor internet connection, inadequate IT equipment, etc.) distract me from following the classes/doing my assignments.	.35**	.14	.25**
3. I find following the classes via videoconference tiresome.	.31**	.15	.23**
4. I believe that the teacher gives interesting lectures.	-.30**	-.26**	-.28**
5. I have been successfully mastering the content of the course.	-.47**	-.49**	-.48**
6. I find doing my assignments demanding.	.42**	.50**	.45**
7. Online learning is a pleasant experience for me.	-.30**	-.30**	-.29**
8. I'm satisfied with French/Italian online learning.	-.40**	-.27**	-.33**
9. I don't find online classes boring.	-.34**	-.23**	-.28**
10. I find it easy to be active.	-.48**	-.38**	-.43**
11. I can have high-quality communication with my teacher.	-.45**	-.41**	-.43**
12. I feel better in online learning of French/Italian now than at the beginning of the academic year.	-.12	-.22*	-.17*
13. I believe that the examination is objective.	-.16	-.21*	-.19**
14. I like the atmosphere during French/Italian online learning via videoconference.	-.33**	-.29*	-.31**
15. I find it difficult to maintain interaction with my colleagues.	.37**	.23*	.31**
16. Physical distance from my colleagues and teachers makes me relaxed.	-.07	-.08	-.07
17. I'm afraid of technical difficulties (e.g., interruption in the internet connection, etc.).	.34**	.13	.24**
18. I'm afraid that I won't know how to use digital technology.	.28**	.39**	.33**

Note: **p < .01, *p < .05

To examine the correlation between the features of online learning and foreign language anxiety in online learning of French and Italian, the FLOLAS, which has been previously presented in this paper, was used.

The FLA in online learning of French and Italian was consistently correlated with several items about the features specific to online learning in both French and Italian subsamples (Table 4). In both subsamples, it was negatively correlated with items 1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 14, and this was statistically significant. The correlations ranged from low to moderately strong. In other words, those who experience higher anxiety in online learning of these foreign languages also tend to find the classes less interesting, perceive the teacher's lectures as being not so high-quality, struggle more with the learning of the course content, have a less pleasant experience with online learning, and are less satisfied with foreign language online learning. They are less active, find the classes more boring, find it difficult to establish high-quality communication with the teacher, and are less pleased with the atmosphere during

foreign language lessons via videoconference. Both subsamples also showed a statistically significant positive correlation between foreign language anxiety in online learning and items 6 and 18. This indicates that those who experience higher anxiety in online language learning also have a greater fear of failure when using digital technology, and perceive the tasks presented to them as more challenging.

Only in the French subsample, there was a positive correlation with items 2 and 3. In other words, those with higher anxiety also experience more fatigue during videoconference classes and are more disrupted by technical difficulties in following the classes and completing tasks. Only in the Italian subsample, there was a negative correlation with items 12 and 13. It is evident that, among the students learning Italian, those who experience higher anxiety also show less improvement in their progressive adaptation to online learning compared to the beginning of the academic year and feel that the assessment of their knowledge is less objective.

Discussion

On one hand, the advent of online education has certainly revolutionized foreign language learning due to its flexibility and accessibility. However, on the other hand, the online environment poses various challenges, including anxiety in foreign language online learning.

Learning a foreign language in an online environment can have positive effects in reducing anxiety compared to learning in a traditional classroom because online tools can reduce the stress of public speaking and allow for a more flexible engagement. However, in online learning, FLA can increase due to the impact of various factors such as reduced interaction and technical issues, which can further increase the feelings of anxiety and isolation, thereby negatively affecting the process of acquiring a foreign language. Several factors can cause or intensify anxiety, such as poor internet connection, and audio or video disturbances, which particularly hinder listening and understanding and can be frustrating. In online learning, immediate feedback may be lacking, which can also cause discomfort. Some, however, believe that online environment lacks the dynamic interaction needed for better language acquisition, which can contribute to increased anxiety over time.

In the research conducted so far, foreign language anxiety in online learning has been studied in correlation with various variables, but these studies were mostly focused on anxiety in learning the English language. Thus, e.g., Li and Du (2023) found in their research that students' anxiety in online English classes has a certain correlation with gender, grade, test score, and their self-concept. In her research on foreign language learning anxiety in virtual classrooms among Tunisian students of English, Leila Najeh Bel'kiry (2022) found a significant relationship between foreign language anxiety and the academic level. Doctorate students are less anxious than M.A. students who experienced a lower level of anxiety in comparison with license (undergraduate) students. She has revealed that there is no significant relationship between gender and foreign language learning anxiety. Let us also mention the results of Novak Lađarević (2021), whose insights into the Croatian educational context are very interesting and show factors that had an impact on students' anxiety among online learners of English for special purposes (ESP), including speech anxiety, evaluation and comprehension anxiety, online ESP classroom environment, anxiety of talking to native speakers, and a lack of motivation for online class attendance. Speech anxiety and fear of negative evaluation are confirmed as the most dominant aspects of language anxiety,

accompanied by fear of a lack of comprehension (Novak Lađarević, 2021: 135). To alleviate anxiety among language learners, Saffari et al. (2024: 75) propose practical strategies tailored to effectively mitigate foreign language anxiety (FLA) and support learners: „implementing cooperative learning activities, providing constructive feedback, creating a positive learning atmosphere, addressing individual student needs, giving clear instructions, and establishing a continuous support system“ (Saffari et al. 2024: 72).

It is evident from the literature that research on FLA in online learning predominantly focuses on English language learning. However, a growing number of studies are exploring the FLA in online learning of languages other than English (LOTE), for example, in learning Spanish (Donahoe, 2010; Money Penny & Aldrich, 2022) or French (Tutton & Cohen, 2024; Wang, 2023). Therefore, the contribution of this paper is especially applicable to the LOTE context, as it highlights the particularities related to anxiety in the online learning of French and Italian.

As expected, the study has shown that anxiety is present in the online learning of French and Italian. Using the FLOLAS with both student subgroups, those learning French and those learning Italian, it was found that the average level of anxiety was below the theoretical midpoint of the scale. After comparing the respondents' anxiety levels, there was no statistically significant difference between the two subgroups. Students with higher levels of anxiety, as measured by the FLOLAS, had a more negative experience with online classes. Anxiety was not related to their language proficiency level, but it was found that those who had been learning these two foreign languages longer experienced less anxiety. It became evident that anxiety is consistently correlated with several items about the features specific to online learning. Both subgroups, as well as the total sample, showed the highest correlation to items 5, 6, 10, and 11, indicating that FLA significantly impacts students' perception of being less successful in mastering the course content, finding tasks more challenging, being less active, and struggling to establish a high-quality communication with the teacher.

Conclusion

The contributions of this paper lie in the creation of the Foreign Language Online Learning Anxiety Scale (FLOLAS), a valid measuring instrument for studying FLA in online environment, as well as insights and a better understanding of anxiety in the online learning of French and Italian. The designed scale can serve as a valuable tool for identifying and measuring FLA in online language learning settings. The reliability index check of the Foreign Language Online Learning Anxiety Scale (FLOLAS) consisting of five items indicated good reliability in both subsamples. Still, there are limitations related to the instruments used that we would like to point out. An English version of the questionnaire, which was given to the respondents in Croatian, has not been verified. Therefore, future research using the presented measuring instrument would need additional verification as to the scale's validity if a version translated into another foreign language is used. Also, it is recommended that the factor structure of the scale be verified on a new sample.

Since most of the research and published papers so far have focused on the topic of anxiety in the online learning of the English language, the exceptional importance of this paper for the context of LOTE becomes clearer. The insights presented in this paper can serve as guidelines that can help teachers when designing foreign language

online teaching to create such an environment, and use such methods that will reduce students' anxiety levels, thereby making the learning process more effective.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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